

Synthesis of Substituted Diphenylamine-2 Carboxylic Acid Hydrazides and Their Condensation Products with Carbonyl Compounds

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4-Nitro diphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid hydrazide and 5-chloro diphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid hydrazide, synthesised by the hydrazinolysis of methyl (or ethyl) diphenylamine-2-carboxylates were condensed with aromatic aldehydes and ketones. The compounds thus obtained were evaluated for their antibacterial activity.

RECENTLY we have described the synthesis of certain diphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid hydrazides and related products¹⁻³. Several such compounds have shown antitubercular activity. In view of these observations and the fact that incorporation of a nitro or a halogeno group in certain biologically active compounds results in enhanced activity^{4,5}, the work on diphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid hydrazides has been enlarged to include 4-nitro and 5-chloro derivatives.

4-Nitro (and 5-chloro) diphenylamine-2-carboxylic acids prepared via Ullmann condensation⁶ were esterified with methanol (or ethanol) and thionyl chloride. The methyl (or ethyl) esters were then treated with hydrazine hydrate. The hydrazides (I) thus obtained were condensed with different carbonyl compounds to yield II and III. I, II and III thus synthesised were evaluated for their antibacterial properties.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillaries and are not corrected. Infrared spectra were recorded

on a Perkin-Elmer 1 37 G Spectrophotometer in KBr.

4-Nitro diphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid hydrazide

4-Nitrodiphenylamino-2-carboxylic acid⁶ (20 g), methanol (250 ml) and thionyl chloride (20 ml) were refluxed under anhydrous conditions for 12 hr. Excess of methanol was distilled off and the remaining viscous residue was treated with 250 ml of water. It was then neutralised with 10% sodium carbonate. The crude methyl ester thus obtained was suspended in 100 ml of ethanol. To this suspension, 12 ml of 99% hydrazine hydrate was added and the whole was refluxed for 10 hr. Excess of solvent was removed under vacuum and the hydrazide thus separated was filtered and recrystallised from dilute ethanol, m.p. 136°-37°, yield 60%.

5-Chlorodiphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid hydrazide was obtained in a 50% yield by following the same procedure, m.p. 152°.

Condensation of I with aldehydes (II)

In a typical reaction, 4-nitro-diphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid hydrazide (2.72 g, 0.01 mole) and benzaldehyde (1.06 g) were refluxed in 25 ml of 95% ethanol for 4 hr. The solid product thus separated was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 203°-04°.

Condensation of I with ketones (III)

5-Chloro-diphenylamino-2-carboxylic acid hydrazide (2.61 g) was dissolved in 25 ml of hot ethanol containing two drops of AcOH. To this solution 1.20 g of acetophenone was added. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 5 hr. and thereafter concentrated to half of its volume. The product separated on cooling was purified by repeated crystallisations from acetone, yield 60%, m.p. 184°.

Biological Data

The compounds listed in the Table 1 were evaluated for their antibacterial activity against four micro-organisms : *Escherichia coli*, *Bacillus magaterium*,

Staphylococcus aureus and *Salmonella typhi* by agar diffusion technique⁷. The zones of inhibition around the discs were measured after an incubation (37°) period of 24 hr. The results of the antibacterial screening are summarised in Table 1.

TABLE I

I

S.N.	R ₁	R ₂	Molecular formula	m.p. °C	% Nitrogen		Antibacterial activity against*			
					Calcd.	Found	<i>E.coli</i>	<i>B.magaterium</i>	<i>S.aureus</i>	<i>S.typhi</i>
1. ^a	NO ₂	H	C ₁₃ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₃	136-37	20.58	20.67	+	-	+	++
2.	H	Cl	C ₁₃ H ₁₂ ClN ₃ O	152	16.06	16.42	++	++	++	-

 II (3-8 R₁ = NO₂; R₂ = H; 9-12 R₁ = H, R₂ = Cl)

S.N.	R ₃	Molecular formula	m.p.	Calcd. % N	Found % N	<i>E.coli</i>	<i>B.magaterium</i>	<i>S.aureus</i>	<i>S.typhi</i>
3.	H	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₃	203-04	15.55	15.36	+	-	-	-
4.	4-OH	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₄	263	14.89	14.76	+	+	+	+
5.	4-NO ₂	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ N ₅ O ₅	265	17.28	17.35	+	-	+	-
6.	4-Cl	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ ClN ₄ O ₃	207-08	14.20	14.20	-	+	-	+
7. ^b	4-Br	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ BrN ₄ O ₃	215-16	12.76	12.73	-	-	-	-
8.	4-OCH ₃	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₄	204	14.35	14.00	+	-	-	-
9.	4-OH	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ ClN ₃ O ₂	228	11.49	11.40	+	-	++	-
10.	4-Cl	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ Cl ₂ N ₃ O	189-90	10.93	11.05	-	+	-	+
11. ^c	4-Br	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ BrClN ₃ O	188	9.80	9.80	++	+	-	-
12.	4-OCH ₃	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ ClN ₃ O ₂	167	11.07	11.16	+	++	-	+

 III (13-14 R₁ = NO₂, R₂ = H; 15-16 R₁ = H, R₂ = Cl)

13.	CH ₃	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₃	184-85	14.97	15.00	-	++	-	-
14.	C ₂ H ₅	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₃	154	14.43	14.40	++	+	+	+
15.	CH ₃	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ ClN ₃ O	184	11.55	11.16	+	-	-	+
16.	C ₂ H ₅	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ ClN ₃ O	165-66	11.13	11.00	-	++	-	+

I.R.(μ) : a, 3.10 (NH), 6.30 (-C-N), 6.70 and 7.60 (NO₂);

b, 3.15 (NH); 6.30 (-C-N), 6.70 and 7.60 (NO₂);

c, 3.15 (NH); 6.30 (-C-N).

- = No inhibition

+ = Zone size 6-8 mm

++ = Zone size greater than 8 mm.

All compounds were obtained in yields ranging from 50-70%.

It has been observed that, in general, the compounds with a chloro substituent were more active when compared with corresponding nitro analogs.

Four compounds (5, 7, 13, 14) were screened for their antitubercular activity against *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* var. *hominis*, strain H₃₇ R_v and were found to be devoid of any activity.

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